

ATTACHMENT 1

Detailed information on relevant stakeholders and their roles in the project:

A. public and state administration bodies

- **Žilina Self-Governing Region** as:
 - the entity responsible for the implementation and supervision of the project.
 - regional policy maker and decision-maker: Utilizing project outputs to refine regional policies and strategies. Provider of multiple vulnerable buildings across the region, such as social service facilities, hospitals, and schools. Detailed knowledge of the region, responsible for implementing development priorities.
- **Municipal authorities (mayors, local crisis management)** – Local implementation of risk mitigation measures, collection of impact data, and communication with citizens.
- **Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic** – the entity responsible for crisis management, Firefighters and Police Corps. Data on all the extraordinary events including extreme rainfalls on the national scale.
- **Emergency medical services (OH ZZS)** – ensures the provision of urgent pre-hospital health care to a person in a condition where their life or health is at risk. Data on response to heat-related health issues.

B. Infrastructure management

- **Road Administration of the ZSK** - the organization responsible for the construction, maintenance and repair of regional roads (Roads class II and III). Information on road damage caused by extreme rainfall and their technical condition, completed and planned investments.
- **Slovak Road Administration** – national road network (Class I roads, expressways). Information about road damage caused by extreme rainfall.
- **National Motorway Company of Slovakia** – most of expressways and all motorways. Information about road damage caused by extreme rainfall.
- **Railways of the Slovak Republic** – information on railway infrastructure and damage caused by extreme rainfall.
- **Regional tourism organization** – the organization responsible for the coordination of activities in the tourism sector at the regional level, coordinates all subregional tourism organizations that bring together all tourism entities in their territory. Knowledge of the tourism sector.
- **Major tourism centres** – those that are not members of regional tourism organizations, however their impact on the economic and social environment must be recognized. Knowledge of the tourism sector.

C. Expert group

- providing technical and methodological support (e.g. hazard modelling, data interpretation etc.), consisting of nine members from following institutions / fields:
- **Academic and research institutions** (Slovak Technical University, National Forest Centre)

- **Environmental non-governmental organizations** (WWF Slovakia, Drop of Rajecká Valley)
- **Regional tourism board** (Žilina Tourist Region)
- **Local municipality** (City of Ružomberok)
- **Regional development**
- **Urban planning**
- **Landscape planning and adaptation to climate change**